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CLASSROOM TECHNOLOGY USAGE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING (ELL & ELT)

Khadija Muhammad Abdullah

Accounting Dep. Lebanese French University-Erbil-Iraq

Abstract

In language teaching and learning, we have a lot to choose from the world of technology: Radio, TV, CD Rom, Computers, C.A.L.L., the Internet, Electronic Dictionary, Email, Blogs and Audio Cassettes, Power Point, Videos, DVD's or VCD's. The recent decades have witnessed a revolution regarding start of technology, and have changed the dynamics of various industries, and has also influence on the industries and the way people interact and work in the society. This rapid rising and development of information technology has offered a better pattern to study the new teaching model. Therefore technology plays a very important role in English teaching. Applying multimedia to create a context to teach English has its unique advantages. We studied the effect of teaching and learning with technology on student cognitive and affective outcomes applying the available technique. Screening studies obtained from an electric search of databases led to 58 studies (2013-2014). Generally, effect sizes were small to moderate across the cognitive and affective outcome measures. Specific teaching/learning components such as challenging activity, context/making sense, instructional conversation, and joint productivity were associated with effect sizes. Instructional features like objectives, pattern of student computer use, and type of learning task also moderated effect sizes. Suggestions are made for teachers to include these instructional features and teaching strategies in teaching and learning along with classroom technology.

Keywords

Technology, Teaching and learning, Computer-assisted instruction, Good instructional practices, Student outcomes

Introduction

Applying technology in classroom teaching and learning has been an important subject in the last few decades. Several meta-analyses have been carried out to examine specific modes of instruction or educational practices that enhance student learning and teaching with technology. Lou, Abrami, and d'Apollonia (2001), for example, studied the effects of small group versus individual instruction along with technology. They found that small-group learning had more positive effects compared with individual learning. Other meta-analyses in technology have investigated topics like the effect of computer-assisted instruction (CAI) on beginning readers (Blok, Oostdam, Otter, and

Overmaat, 2002,) CAI in science education (Bayraktar, 2002), the way interactive distance education is effective (Cavanaugh, 2001), and the technology impact on reading in grades 6-8 (Moran, Ferdig, Pearson, Wardrop, & Blomeyer, 2008). A recent meta-analysis by Li and Ma (2010) studied the impact of computer technology on mathematics achievement in K-12 classrooms from 46 papers and found a greater influence for elementary over secondary school students and that the technology impact was bigger when constructivist approach was applied in the teaching and learning process (Li & Ma, 2010). A more comprehensive meta-analysis for the impact of technology on learning was carried out applying a second-order meta-analytic technique involving 25 metaanalyses including 1055 studies in a 40 year span (Tamim, Bernard, Borokhovski, Abrami, & Schmid, 2011).

However, these recent reviews focused only on a specific issue (e.g. group size, CAI, or the general technology effect) and there is little information on what the effective strategies or suitable approaches are in integrating and applying technology in schools and classrooms. For example, Moran et al's paper (2008) found not much research including outcomes on metacognition and use of strategy. Ma & Li's investigation (2010), on the other hand, reported a differential effect on constructivist approach versus traditional approach but no specific teaching strategies or instructional features were informed. Similarly, Tamim et al's study (2011), though very inclusive and comprehensive, only included 2 moderator variables on grade level and aim of technology use. As Ross, Morrison, and Lowther (2010) commented that "educational technology is not a homogeneous 'intervention' but a wide variety of modalities, tools, and strategies for learning. Therefore, its effectiveness depends on how well it assists teachers and students achieve the desired instructional aims" (p. 19), in line with this statement, we aimed to investigate what the effective practices are in order that teachers and students can teach and learn effectively with technology.

Purpose of this study

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effects of teaching and learning with technology on student outcomes in K-12 settings in order to inform instructional practices, by reviewing the experimental and quasi-experimental researches published between 1997 and 2011. Unlike previous syntheses, which may focus on a particular teaching practice, grade level, or subject area, we are interested in the overall impact and common technology features, teaching strategies, and instructional characteristics that are beneficial to student learning and teaching across grade levels. Specifically the meta-analysis aim is to address the following research questions:

- . What is the general magnitude and direction of the relationship between teaching and learning with technology and student outcomes?
- . Are there specific technology features, teaching strategies, and instructional characteristics that have impact on teaching and learning with technology on student outcomes?

In the following section, we provided a brief review and rationale for the coding of variables based on teaching strategies, technology characteristics, and instructional characteristics.

Technology characteristics

Technology role and computer use pattern

Technology can have several roles in education, for instance, role of productivity, role of delivery system, or resources. Computer programs were recognized most effective in helping student centered learning if the programs can provide scaffolds for students with support factual knowledge acquisition, special needs, and emphasize technology capacity in making students' new learning experiences (Pedersen & Liu, 2003). Besides, significant learning achievements were found if computers used as resources (Wegerif, 2004). Pattern of using computer concerns the size of participants working together with technology. Unlike working with technology individually has greater flexibility for participants to adjust their own pace, working in a larger group (e.g. 6-8 or more) may result in the broad application of the technology by one or a few persons. Research has demonstrated that students

working in small groups (e.g. 3-5) with computers did better than student working individually with computers (Lou, Abrami, and d' Apollonia, 2001).

Type of technology, software, and objective of technology

Type of technology means the carriers (e.g. PCs, laptops, PDAs...etc.) of the instructional material whereas software is a type of instructional material itself (e.g. exploratory environment tutorial, drill & practice...etc). For example, laptop programs were found to be effectual in student engagement (Penuel, 2006) and academic accomplishment (Zucker & Hug, 2008). Software, on the other hand, can be very handful if used for an suitable learning purpose. For instance, multimedia talking books can assist beginning readers learn to read (Chera & Wood, 2003; Doty, Popplewell, Byers, 2001) and computer simulations can aid learn dissection before the actual laboratory anatomy in a biology class (Akpan & Andre, 2000). As for objectives of technology use, technology was found to be more effective in learning when applied to support instruction in comparison to for direct instruction (Tamim et al, 2011).

Effective Teaching Strategies

We used teaching strategies as moderators in the meta-analysis. The Center for Research on Education, Excellence, and Diversity developed five standards of effective teaching strategies: (1) Teachers and Students Producing Together (Joint Productive Activity), (2) Making Meaning: Linking School to Students' Lives (Contextualization), (3) Developing Language and Literacy Across the Curriculum (Language Development, (4) Teaching Through Conversation (Instructional Conversation) (see Dalton, 1998; Tharp, 1997) (5) Teaching Complex Thinking (Challenging Activities). The bases for these standards are the best empirical and theoretical knowledge in the field, and there is plentiful evidence that their application in classrooms may result in great improvements for the education of all students (Tharp, Estrada, Dalton, & Yamauchi, 2000).

Instructional features

Mode of instruction and role of teacher

Form of instruction can be discussed in diversity in settings, such as individualized instruction, small-group and whole-class. Waxman and Huang (1996) found whole-class approaches were frequently observed in the classrooms with lower technology use. In these classes, students generally listened to and watched the teacher, while more independent work was observed in classrooms where technology was moderately applied. Studies also showed that teachers' role as facilitator for student learning had a higher effect than as disseminator of knowledge or modeling processes (Dekker and Elshout-Mohr, 2004; Stonewater, 2005; McCrone, 2005).

Type of task, task difficulty, and learning responsibility

Type of task for learning can be problem solving, basic skills/factual learning, or inquiry/investigation project-based learning. Project-based learning, for instance, was found to have dramatic gains in student academic achievement across states in the U.S. (Thomas, 2000). In the teaching strategy section, task difficulty is similar to challenging activity in order to teach complex thinking. Learning responsibility can be divided into student-centered, teacher directed, mixed or system-directed. Currently, there is a tendency to call for student-centered learning (Jonassen, 2000).

Methods

For this meta-analytic review, we employed selection criteria and review methods that are similar to latest major national reviews carried out in areas like reading (International Reading Panel, 2002) and teacher preparation (Wilson, Floden, & Ferrini-Mundy, 2001). Evaluation studies that have been published in refereed journals during a fifteen-year period (1997-2011) and the synthesis included quasi-experimental, experimental, and quantitative research and.

Selection of articles

Articles must have the criteria bellow to be included in the synthesis:

- Focus on teaching and learning with technology in K–12 classroom contexts where students and their teachers have primarily face-to-face interact (> 50 percent of the time);
- Compare the group at the beginning of the intervention (pretest) to a posttest measure, or; and Compare a technology group to a nontechnology comparison group
- Enjoy reported statistical data (e.g., *t* tests or *F* tests) that allowed the calculation of effect sizes.

First, online computer databases such as PsycInfo or Education Resources Information Center (ERIC) were applied for finding articles. Keywords such as “Technology/computer” and “achievement” or “technology/computer” and “attitude” or “technology/computer” along with “student outcome” were entered in the databases. Over 500 articles were left and met the desired publication time for coverage. Abstracts about these articles were then read to in order to know if they are relevant to the synthesis. Most of the studies were discarded because they did not compare the experiment group to a control group with lack of technology access. Other papers were excluded because they are not directly connected directly with the usage of technology for learning and teaching aim in the K-12 setting. The search and selection proper procedures led to a collection of 58 papers.

Coding design

Our studies were coded on 17 variables. The study descriptors included 2 variables: publication features (technology journal or educational journal) and grade level. Technology characteristic descriptors consisted of 5 variables: objective of technology use, type of software, role of technology, type of technology, and pattern of student computer use. The instructional descriptors included 5 variables: task difficulty, learning responsibility, mode of instruction, type of *136* learning tasks, and role of teacher. We included the Five Standards for Effective Pedagogy developed by the Center for Research on Education, Diversity, and Excellence (2002; see Dalton, 1998; Tharp, 1997) as for teaching strategy descriptors.

Interrate reliability

From the 58 studies, two investigators independently coded the papers on the basis of the coding book of 17 features for each of the 366 effect sizes. Then, each investigator independently coded six papers from the other investigator. The intercoder agreement for each study reviewed was greater than the 85-percent criterion and the average Cohen’s Kappa coefficient reached 0.88

Data analysis

The basis of the overall data analysis strategies was Lipsey and Wilson (2001). In the earliest coding of studies, two kinds of student results were identified: (1) cognitive, and (2) affective. if means, standard deviations, and group size were reported in the selected papers, effect sizes of standardized mean difference were comuted. Otherwise, effects were calculated from *t*-statistics or *F*-statistics if these were reported. Hedges and Olkin estimator in Lipsey and Wilson (2001) were used in order to make unbiased effect size estimates (i.e., Hedge’s *g*), which are weighted with

inverse variance weight, the inverse of squared standard error value, in order that effects with larger standard error are given a smaller weight because large standard error produces less precise effect size values. a single combined ES was extracted from each investigation for each of the two results as suggested by Lipsey and Wilson (2001) in order to insure the independence of ESs,.

Q-statistics were resulted for each result based on the adjusted mean effect size weighted with the inverse variance weight function within each paper to study the heterogeneity of effect size (Lipsey & Wilson, 2001). The Q-statistic proceed a chi-square distribution with degrees of freedom is equal to $k-1$, where k is the number of effect sizes (Hedges & Olkin, 1985). Lipsey and Wilson (2001) evaluated moderators applying the meta-analytic analog to analysis of variance. A significant Q_b (Q statistic between) suggest a significant mean difference between/among levels of categorical variable in interpreting the Q statistic, while a significant Q_w (Q statistic within) evaluates the heterogeneity within groups and shows that a moderator may be needed for group studies to be divided into homogenous subcategories (Lipsey & Wilson, 2001). In the case of need for analysis of moderator effect in order to study sources of variation in effect sizes, a Bonferroni correction with alpha level of .005 will be selected for the analysis in order to avoid inflated experiment-wise Type I error rate while numerous analyses were done for each result.

Results

A total of 366 effect sizes were calculated from 58 studies used in the study. Mean effect sizes were computed for each construct across studies. From 48 studies, the weighted mean effect (Hedge's g) was 0.42 with 243 effects for the cognitive outcome. From 21 studies, the effect was 0.18 with 92 effects for the affective outcome.

The chi-square Q statistic was calculated for each result to evaluate the homogeneity of the mean effects. For the cognitive outcome, $Q (df =47) = 231.47, p < .001$; for the affective outcome, $Q (df =20) = 118.60, p < .001$. The large Q statistics and small p values brought to light heterogeneity of the effect sizes within each construct. Therefore, we carried analyses of the moderator effect for both outcome measures.

Moderator analysis

Cognitive

Results for the cognitive outcome were displayed in Table 1. For effect sizes, grade, context/ sense making, objective, pattern of student computer use, and type of learning task were significant moderators. Compared with grade K-3 with mean effect (.50), grade 4-6 with mean effect (.41), and grade 7-8 with mean effect (.59), grade 9-12 enjoyed the lowest one (.22). The finding was similar with Li and Ma's investigations (2010) where secondary schools had a lower effect. Studies showing evidence of making sense or teaching and learning in context (.53) had higher mean effects than those without evidence (.39). Applying technology for remediation of skill not learned (.83), finding out about ideas and information (.61), and expressing themselves in writing (.59) had greater effects than for multiple objectives (.19), information analysis (.39), or others (.26). Studies that report project-based learning (1.39), factual learning (.64), inquiry/investigation (.61), and others (.62) had greater mean effects than those reporting mixed type learning (.05) and problem-solving (.39). A differential effect was also found on pattern of student computer use. Three to five students for each computer had the greatest mean effect (1.08) followed by two students for each computer (.65), mixed pattern (.57), and others (.44). One student per computer had the lowest mean effect size (.40).

Table 1. Categorical moderators for cognitive outcomes

Variable	Mean	QB	dfB	Prob(QB)	Qw	dfw	Prob(Qw)
Overall	0.42						
GRADE		15.49	3	.0014	191.76	43	< .0001
24=K-3	0.50						
25=4-6	0.41						
26=7-8	0.59						
27=9-12	0.22						
Publication feature		7.86	1	.0051	199.40	45	< .0001
1=technology	0.41						
2= educational	0.66						
Type of Technology		5.49	4	.2408	124.85	27	< .0001
1=PCs	.56						
2=Laptops	.88						
3= Networked computer	.39						
5=Multimedia	.61						
6=Other	.44						
Software		6.70	4	.1529	187.07	33	< .0001
1=Tutorial	.81						
2=Drill-and- Practice	.42						
3= Exploratory Environment	.38						
4=Tools for other task	.59						
6=Other	.41						
Role of Technology		6.82	3	.0779	177.21	38	< .0001
1=Productivity	.41						
2=Delivery system	.43						
3=Resources	.45						
4=Other	.24						
Pattern of Computer Use		21.13	4	.0008	60.31	27	.0002
3=1 student per computer	.40						
4=2 students per computer	.65						
5= 3-5 students per computer	1.08						
7=Mixed pattern	.57						
8=Other	.44						
Objective		51.20	5	< .0001	148.67	38	< .0001
1=Remediation	.83						
2=Expressing themselves in writing	.59						
4=Finding out about information	.61						
5=Analyzing information	.39						
10=Multiple objectives	.19						
11=Other	.26						
Context/Making Sense		9.00	1	.0027	196.25	40	< .0001
1=No evidence	.39						
2=Some evidence	.53						
Challenging activities		7.47	2	.0239	197.77	43	< .0001
1=No evidence	.28						
2=Some evidence	.42						
3=Extensive evidence	.51						
Instructional conversation		.8264	2	.6615	204.41	43	< .0001
1=No evidence	.39						
2=Some evidence	.43						
3=Extensive evidence	.45						

Joint Productivity /Collaboration	6.77	2	.0338	198.47	43	<.0001
1=No evidence	.42					
2=Some evidence	.54					
3=Extensive evidence	.32					
Language Literacy Development	7.12	1	.0076 1	98.12	44	<.0001
1= No evidence	.39					
2= Some evidence	.53					
Task difficulty	5.145	3	.1615	113.13	26	<.0001
1=Difficult	.35					
2=Moderately difficult	.58					
3=Not difficult	.88					
4=Mixed level of difficulty	.42					
Type of learning task	52.31	5	<.0001	139.20	37	<.0001
1=Basic skill/factual learning	.64					
2=Problem-solving	.39					
3=Inquiry/Investigation	.61					
4=Project-based	1.39					
5=Mixed-Type	.05					
6=Other	.62					
Learning responsibility	8.72	3	.0333	131.26	35	<.0001
1=Student-controlled	.31					
2=Teacher-directed	.54					
3=System-directed	.43					
4=Mixed	.57					
Mode of Instruction	6.29	4	.1783	120.77	33	<.0001
1=Whole-group	.47					
2=paired	.48					
3=Small-group (3-5)	.48					
4=Individualized	.39					
5=Mixed	.55					
Role of teacher	11.87	3	.0078	50.2176	22	<.0001
2=Facilitator	.62					
3=Modeling processes	-.39					
4=Mixed	.61					
5=Other	.39					

Affective

Results for affective outcome were presented in Tables 2. Challenging activities, instructional conversation, and joint productivity/collaboration were significant moderators for effect sizes. Studies displaying some evidence (.36) or extensive evidence (.25) of challenging activities had greater mean effects compared to those without evidence of challenging activities (.06). Similarly, studies with some evidence of instructional conversation (.44) presented greater effect sizes than those without evidence of instructional conversation (.12). Those studies reporting some evidence (.34) or extensive evidence (.32) of joint productivity/collaboration which also had greater mean effects in the affective outcome than those without evidence (.06) of joint productivity/collaboration.

Table 2. Categorical Moderators for Affective Outcomes

Variable	Mean	QB	dfB	Prob(QB)	Qw	dfw	Prob(Qw)
Overall	.18						
GRADE		7.33	3	.0619	115.18	17	<.0001
24=K-3	.17						
25=4-6	.13						
26=7-8	.60						
27=9-12	.21						
Publication feature		.33	1	.5645	122.18	19	<.0001
1=technology	.19						
2= educational	.07						
Type of Technology		10.89	3	.0123	19.04	12	.0876
1=PCs .30							
3= Networked-computer	.07						
5=Multimedia	.38						
6=Other	.04						
Role of Technology		7.45	3	.0589	25.77	10	.0041
1=Productivity	.04						
2=Delivery system	.29						
3=Resources	.17						
4=Other	.21						
Objective		8.50	5	.1304	28.28	13	.0083
1=Remediation	.17						
4=Finding out about ideas And information	.30						
5=Analyzing information	.64						
7= Improving Computer Skills	1.07						
10=Multiple objectives	.16						
Pattern of Student Computer Use		1.05	3	.7881	7.2091	6	.3019
3=One student	.19						
4=Two student	.37						
7=Mixed pattern	.29						
Context/Making Sense		5.40	1	.0201	38.70	18	.0031
1=No evidence	.10						
2=Some evidence	.27						
Challenging activities		12.69	2	.0018	31.41	17	.0178
1=No evidence	.06						
2=Some evidence	.36						
3=Extensive evidence	.25						
Instructional conversation		8.63	1	.0033	35.47	18	.0082
1=No evidence	.12						
2=Some evidence	.44						
Joint Productivity /Collaboration		14.55	2	.0007	29.55	17	.0298
1=No evidence	.06						
2=Some evidence	.34						
3=Extensive evidence	.32						
Language Literacy Development		2.93	1	.0871	41.17	18	.0014
1= No evidence	.11						
2= Some evidence	.23						
Learning responsibility		3.78	3	.2857	19.02	12	.0881
1=Student-controlled	.33						
2=Teacher-directed	.76						
3=System-directed	.17						

4=Mixed	.29						
Mode of Instruction		14.61	4	.0056	1.79	3	.6168
1=Whole-group	1.07						
2=paired	.64						
3=Small group (3-5)	.25						
4=Individualized	.19						
5=Mixed	1.09						
Role of teacher		3.76	2	.1523	9.0719	4	.0593
1=Disseminator	1.07						
2=Facilitator	.25						
5=Other	.19						

Discussion & Conclusions

The main aim of this meta-analysis was to bring together 15 years of investigations on the effect of teaching and learning with technology on student cognitive and affective outcomes. The overall effect sizes for the two outcomes exhibited a positive effect in teaching and learning with technology in terms of magnitude and direction.

In particular, cognitive outcome had an effect size (.42) that was larger than several of the previous meta-analytic reviews, which were old or including several decades of studies (e.g. Bayraktar, 2002; Christmann & Badgett, 2003; Kulik and Kulik, 1991; Ouyang, 1990; Tamim et al., 2011) but was comparable with meta-analyses analyzing new studies (e.g. Li & Ma, 2010; Moran et al., 2008). It is possible that effect sizes increased with the evolution of technology itself and the improvement of pedagogy in teaching and learning along with technology.

Suggestions for pre-service and in-service teachers

On the basis of the meta-analytic review, we obtained valuable information regarding the best practices in teaching and learning with technology. For the cognitive outcome, we found technology was best use for the aim of basic skills and factual learning which refers to “rote learning and the degree to which participants were able to repeat facts given during the lesson” (p. 800, Jang, 2008). Rote or factual learning is relatively less complex and less difficult compared to other purposes since it applies a plainer strategy to learning, such as memorization (Vansteenkiste, Simons, Lens, Soenens, & Matos, 2005). Nevertheless, acquiring basic skills or factual learning is an essential step for students to employ technology for other ends like expressing themselves in writing, finding out information, analyzing information, and multiple purposes. Our argument can be verified by the fact that project based learning also made the highest effect in regard to type of learning task. The scope of project-based learning usually span across subjects and assist learners to see the interconnectedness of multiple domains; it encourages students to look for information, exchange findings, find out about facts, and collaborate with their peers (Kwok & Tan, 2004). Each of steps for these knowledge building were anchored upon basic skills/ factual learning and instructional elements that are sense-making and contextualized (Arnseth and Saljot; 2007). Accordingly, for teachers to enhance student cognitive outcomes, the take-home messages are to

- Collaborate in small or paired groups with computers;
- Develop instructional elements that are sense-making in context
- Build student basic skills and assist them see the interconnectedness of subject knowledge in a project-based learning

Also, collaboration is an noteworthy factor for the effective outcome. Besides, by working collaboratively, students not only share their cognitive capacity, reduce their mental efforts, but also boost their confidence in the task, which

in turn result in better affective outcome, especially in processing complex tasks (Kirschner, Paas, Kirschner, 2011). The challenging activity evidence or in some sense similar to task difficulty also had greater student effects. According to the flow theory, people gain their optimal experience in learning and performing while their perceived challenge of task and skill reach a balanced state (Csikszentmihályi, 1990; Moneta & Csikszentmihályi, 1996). Besides, evidence of instructional conversation also promoted student outcome since it is engaging, interesting, focusing on concepts, which are relevant to students and not dominating by any one student in the way that extended discussions are found among students and the teacher (Goldenberg, 1991). Accordingly, the take-home messages for the affective outcome are to include instructional conversation, challenging activities, and joint collaboration or productivity in learning and teaching using computers.

Based on the findings of the study, we would like entreat that professional development and teacher preparation be set up with a broad variety of training scopes to include these investigated technology and pedagogical practices for pre service and in-service teachers in teaching and learning with technology.

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(Asterisks indicate studies included in the meta-analysis.)

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Appendix A: Coding information extracted from reviewed studies

Author	Grade level	Technology tool	Type of task	Outcome /subject measured
Akpan & Andre (2000).	7	PCs-simulation	PS	life science
Alfassi (2000).		NCs	I/I	writing and reading
Alspaugh (1999).	10-12	PCs	BS/FL	Academic achievement (all areas)
Bain et al. (2000)	6-8	NCs-hypertext discussion tool	I/I	Literature
Barker & Ansoorge (2007)	4-6	Robotics.	PS	Science and technology
Biggs et al. (2008).	6-8	NCs–interactive software	BS/FL	reading
Brown et al. (2003).	9-12	NCs – simulation	PBL	academic and technology self-efficacy
Butzin (2001)	K-5	PCs	BS/FL	Reading, writing and math
Cady & Terrell, (2007).	5	PCs	BS/FL	self-efficacy attitudes
Chera & Wood (2003).	K	PCs – multimedia	BS/FL	Reading
Churach & Fisher (2001)	7	NCs Science		
Cohen (2001).	9	PCs	PBL	Learning style
Dixon(1997).	8	PCs	BS/FL	Geometry
Doty et al. (2001).	K	PCs-Interactive storybook	BS/FL	reading
Dybdahl et al. (1997).	5	PCs	BS/FL	Writing
Erdner et al. (1998).	1	PCs	BS/FL	reading
Ekane & Maiken (1997).	7-8	PCs	BS/FL	English vocabulary
Erdogan (2009)	8	PCs	BS/FL	Computer attitude / anxiety
Estep et al. (2000).	3	Integrated Learning System (ILS)	BS/FL	achievement
Funkhouser (2003)	10-11	PCs	BS/FL	Math performance, attitude
Harwell et al. (2001).	6	Tech-integration achievement		
Hertz-Lazarowitz & Bar-Natan(2002).	5-6	NCs -CMC	BS/FL	Writing
Hopson et al.\ (2001-2002).	5-6	NCs	PS	Higher order thinking
Isiksal & Askar (2005).	7	PCs	PS	Math and computer self-efficacy
Keogh et al. (2000)	7-8	PCs	PBL	English language
Ko (2002).	3-5	PCs – computer games	PS	Cognitive skills
Kramarski & Feldman (2000)	8	NCs	BS/FL	reading, motivation, Meta cognitive awareness
Laio & She (2009)	8	PCs-web-based	I/I	Scientific concept change and reasoning
Liu (1998).	3-4	PCs-Hypermedia authoring	PBL	Creative thinking
Liu et al. (1998).	10-12	PCs	BS/FL	Computer attitude, achievement
Lynch et al. (2000).	5-6	PCs	BS/FL	Reading literacy
Lynch et al. (1997).	7-8	PDA's - hand-held texts	I/I	Oracy
Macaruso & Walker (2008)	K	PCs - Multimedia	BS/FL	Literacy skills
Matthew (1997).	3	PCs - Multimedia	BS/FL	Reading
McDonald & Hannafin, (2003).	3	PCs- games	BS/FL	Social studies
McNamara et al. (2006).	8 -9	PCs- Interactive	BS/FL	Reading
Michael (2001).	7	PCs-computer simulation	PBL	Product creativity
Mitchell & Fox (2001).	K	PCs- Multimedia	BS/FL	Phonological awareness
Nicolaou et al. (2007).	4	Computer labs	I/I	Graphic interpretation

Raghavan et al. (1997).	6	PCs	BS/FL	Geometry
Roberts & Stephens (1999).	9	PCs- Interactive	PS	Geometry
Ross et al. (2001).	1-2	PCs- Interactive	BS/FL	Computer skills, self- efficacy
Ross et al. (2009)	7-10	PCs-Interactive web-based tools	PS	fraction
Rotbain et al. (2008).	10-12	PCs-animations	I/I	biology
Shamir et al. (2007).	K	PCs- CD-ROM story book	BS/FL	Literacy
Scheidet (2003).	K-12	PCs- web-based curriculum	I/I	Global History
Segers & Verhoeven (2002).	K	PCs- CD-ROM story book	BS/FL	Literacy
Sherer (1998).	7-12	PCs- simulation games	BS/FL	moral development
Thomas & Hofmeister (2002).	3 - 4	PCs-message board	-	Literacy
Tsou et al. (2002).	6	PCs -Web-based multimedia	BS/FL	EFL
Tusei (2011)	4	PCs-collaborative learning environment	BS/FL	Reading, self-concept
Waxman & Huang (1997).	6 & 8	PCs -Level of tech use		Motivation, anxiety
Weiss et al. (2006).	K	PCs-multimedia (cooperative)	BS/FL	Mathematics & learning style
Wheeler et al (1999)	9	PCs-cognitive tutoring	PS	Word problem-solving
Woodul et al. (2000).	8	PCs-multimedia (cooperative)		Social studies & Self- perception
Yang & Heh (2007)	10	PCs-web-based virtual lab	BS/FL	Computer attitudes, Physics
Yang & Tsai (2010)	6	PCs	BS/FL	Number sense, learning attitude
Ysseldyke et al. (2003).	4&5	PCs- learning information system	BS/FL	mathematics